

**INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL OF
PHARMACEUTICAL SCIENCES**
[ISSN: 0975-4725; CODEN(USA): IJPS00]
Journal Homepage: <https://www.ijpsjournal.com>

Review Paper

Review Of Anjana Formulations in Basavarajeeyam and Their Clinical Significance

Arya J. P.*, Govinda Sharma K., Prajwal Sanakyanavar, Suchindra R., Surabhi Gopal, Gayathri Sajeev

Dept. of Rasashastra and Bhaishajya Kalpana, Sri Dharmasthala Manjunatheshwara college of Ayurveda and Hospital, Hassan. Pincode: 573201.

ARTICLE INFO

Published: 12 May 2026

Keywords:

Anjana, Basavarajeeyam,
Herbo mineral, Kriya Kalpa,
Netra Roga, Rasa Dravya

DOI:

10.5281/zenodo.20133225

ABSTRACT

Background: Basavarajeeyam is an Ayurvedic book authored by Neelakanta Kotturu Basavaraja. This is a 15th-century text which provides information about simple and practical formulations. It comprises 25 prakaraṇa, with the first 24 addressing various rogas and the 25th focusing on rasa dravyas. In the 17th chapter on Netra Roga Nidana-Lakshana-Chikitsa, different Anjana yoga are described, which hold potential for adaptation in clinical practice. **Methods:** The Anjana yoga described in Netra roga Chikitsa Adhyaya of Basavarajeeyam, English Translation by Prof. Dr. M.S. Krishnamurthy, published by Chaukhambha Orientalia, Varanasi, 2019 were enlisted. Those formulations were analysed for composition and indications. **Results:** The study identified 36 distinct Anjana yoga out of which 31 formulations were herbo-mineral formulations. These formulations are indicated for various diseases like Abhishyanda (conjunctivitis) and Timira (cataract). **Discussion:** Anjana is unique as it serves both as a Dinacharya (daily regimen) for preventive health and a Kriyakalpa for curative purposes. High prevalence of mineral compounds was seen in these Anjana yogas. This may be because the minerals, achieve better bioavailability through topical conjunctival application due to their high molecular weights. This observation is an indicator about the depth of understanding the ancient scholars of Ayurveda had while recommending the use of Anjana. **Conclusion:** Basavarajeeyam is a classical Ayurvedic text that presents simple and practical formulations for various diseases, including ocular disorders. This study identified 36 Anjana yoga, with a predominance of Herbo-mineral formulations indicated for conditions like Abhishyanda and Timira. The findings highlight Anjana as an effective topical therapy with both preventive and curative potential in eye care. Further research is needed to validate, standardize, and integrate

***Corresponding Author:** Arya J. P.

Address: PG scholar, Dept. of Rasashastra and Bhaishajya Kalpana, Sri Dharmasthala Manjunatheshwara college of Ayurveda and Hospital, Hassan. Pincode: 573201

Email ✉: jp.aryakannan@gmail.com

Relevant conflicts of interest/financial disclosures: The authors declare that the research was conducted in the absence of any commercial or financial relationships that could be construed as a potential conflict of interest.

these formulations into modern ophthalmic practice.

INTRODUCTION

Basavarajeeyam is a compiled authoritative text written by Neelakanta Kotturu Basavaraja. This book belongs to 15th AD which provides information on formulations in various diseases. It comprises 25 *prakaraṇa*, of which the first 24 deal with various *rogas* and the 25th focuses on *rasa dravyas*. The 17th chapter is dedicated to *Netra Roga Nidhana-Lakshana-Chikitsa*. In this context, Basavaraja mentions about 36 different *Anjana yogas*, that can be used as *kriyakalpa* in *netraroga*¹.

Ayurvedic science have emphasized the importance of the eyes, stating “*Sarvendriyaṇam nayanam pradhanam*,” as they are foremost among all the senses². Ayurvedic classics describe multiple *Kriyakalpas* for the management of *netra rogas*. While *Sushruta* described five *Kriyakalpas* (*Tarpana*, *Putapaka*, *Seka*, *Aschyotana*, and *Anjana*), later authors like *Vagbhata* and *Sharangadhara* expanded these to seven, including *Pindi* and *Vidalaka*. Among these, *Anjana* (collyrium) stands out as the most versatile and practical method for topical ocular drug delivery.

Anjana is indicated not only in ocular disorders but also in certain systemic conditions. However, its clinical use in systemic conditions remains limited due to a lack of critical analysis. *Anjana* involves the application of a superfine paste or powder into the conjunctival sac using a *Shalaka*. Unlike other procedures that require complex clinical setups, *Anjana* is characterized by its ease of administration, cost-effectiveness, and suitability for long-term use. Its significance is further highlighted by its inclusion in *Dinacharya* (daily regimen), where the daily application of *Sauveeranjana* is advocated to maintain ocular health and balance *Kapha Dosha*³.

Compared to systemic therapy, topical methods play a crucial role in the treatment of eye diseases by providing direct drug delivery to ocular tissues. The therapeutic efficacy of *Anjana* lies in its ability to enhance drug bioavailability. Modern pharmacological perspectives suggest that topical application to the eye allows for prolonged contact with the vascularized conjunctival and nasal mucosa. This facilitates rapid absorption, allowing the drug to reach target tissues while bypassing the limitations of the systemic blood-aqueous barrier⁴. In this work, an attempt is made to collect the details of 36 *Anjana* formulations from *Basavarajeeyam*, and critically analyse their composition and therapeutic applications.

Aims And Objectives:

Aim:

To explore and analyse the *Anjana yoga* described in *Basavarajeeyam*.

Objectives:

- To enlist the *Anjana yoga* mentioned in the *Netra Roga Chikitsa Adhyaya*.
- To analyse their composition, with emphasis on herbo-mineral components.
- To study their therapeutic indications in ocular conditions.

MATERIALS AND METHODS:

The *Anjana yoga* described in *Netra roga Chikitsa Adhyaya* of *Basavarajeeyam*, were enlisted and analysed for composition and indications. English translation by Prof. Dr. M.S. Krishnamurthy, published by Chaukhambha Orientalia, Varanasi, 2019 was referred⁵.

Observation and Result

A total of 36 *Anjana yoga* was identified under *Netra Roga Chikitsa*. 31 among them had mineral or herbo mineral composition.

Table 1: Anjana yoga with Herbo mineral ingredients indicated in Specific diseases

Sl No:	Name of Yoga	No: of Ingredients	Rasa Dravya with proportion	% of mineral drugs
1	Trikatukadi Anjana	Total – 25 Herbal - 18 Mineral - 07	Saindhava lavana, Sphatika (4.23%), Rasanjana, Gairika (2.82%), Tuttha (1.41%), Tamra, Shankha (4.23%)	25.95%
2	Kathakaadi Anjana	Total – 13 Herbal - 07 Mineral - 06	Saindhava lavana, Samudraphena, Rasanjana, Manashila, Kukkutanda twak, Shankha *Each 7.69%	46.15%
3	Garudaanjanam 1	Total – 20 Herbal - 10 Mineral - 10	Tuttha, Sphatika, Saindhava lavana, Samudraphena, Hingula, Manashila, Shankha, Kukkutanda twak, Rasanjana *Each 5%	50%
4	Rasakriya 1	Total - 20 Herbal - 09 Mineral - 11	Parada/Rasasindura, Kaseesa, Tamra, Rasanjana, Saindhava lavana, Tuttha, Gairika, Manashila, Souveeranjana, Pravala, Naga *5% each	55%
5	Netranjanam	Total - 08 Herbal - 03 Mineral - 05	Souveeranjana, Rasasindhura, Sphatika, Naga, Teekshna Loha *12.5% each	62.5%
6	Rasanjanadi Anjana 2	Total - 10 Herbal - 02 Mineral - 08	Samudraphena, Sphatika, Hingula, Rasanjana, Kurmaprishta (1.25%), Manashila (6.25%), Saindhava lavana (25%), Loha (25%)	62.5%
7	Chandrakanjana	Total - 20 Herbal - 12 Mineral - 08	Tuttha, Saindhava lavana, Rasasindhura, Harathala, Rasanjana, Tamra, Loha, Shankha *Each 5%	40%
8	Anjana in Timira (Sphatikanjanam)	Total - 14 Herbal - 08 Mineral - 06	Sphatika, Rasanjana, Tuttha, Rasaka, Saindhava lavana, Naga *Each 7.14%	42.86%
9	Anjana Varti	Total - 30 Herbal - 14 Mineral - 16	Manashila(6.66%), Tuttha, Hingula, Haratala, Souveeranjana, Sphatika, Somala/Talaka, Saindhava lavana, Samudraphena, Gairika, Shankha, Tamra, Naga, Abhraka, Kantaloha *Each 3.33% except Manashila	53.33%
10	Nayanaamrutha 2	Total - 07 Herbal - 01 Mineral - 06	Tuttha, Saindhava lavana, Sasyaka, Samudraphena, Rasanjana, Tankana *Each 14.28%	85.71%
11	Tilapushpanjana	Total – 03 Herbal - 02 Mineral - 01	Kharpara (28.57%)	28.57%
12	Kharparadi Anjana	Total – 10 Herbal - 04 Mineral - 06	Kharpara, Tuttha, Samudraphena, Rasanjana, Manashila, Shankha *Each 10%	60%
13	Chandraprabha Anjana	Total – 07 Herbal - 02 Mineral - 05	Samudrapheena, Narakapalasthi, Kukkutanda twak, Manashila, Mundaloha *Each 14.28%	71.43%

14	Chandrodaya Varti	Total – 08 Herbal - 06 Mineral - 02	Shankhanabhi, Manashila *Each 12.5%	25%
15	Narikelanjana	Total – 09 Herbal - 08 Mineral - 01	Saindhava lavana (1.15%) *Coconut water (73.56%)	1.15%
16	Shankhadi vati	Total – 04 Herbal - 01 Mineral - 03	Shankha (51.61%), Manashila (38.71), Saindhava lavana (3.23%)	93.55%
17	Pushpanjanam	Total – 14 Herbal - 09 Mineral - 05	Gairika, Gorochana, Tuttha, Pushpanjana, Shankha *Each 7.14%	35.7%
18	Godanthadi Anjana	Total – 13 Herbal - 03 Mineral - 10	Godanti, Kukkutanda, Samudraphena, Shankha, Varatika, Tamra, Sphatika, Makaradanta, Sarangadanta, Tuttha *Each 7.69%	76.92%
19	Utpaladi Anjana	Total – 06 Herbal - 05 Mineral - 01	Saindhava lavana (16.67%)	16.67%
20	Ardhachandrodaya Anjana	Total – 11 Herbal - 08 Mineral - 03	Sphatika, Gairika, Tuttha *Each 9.09%	27.27%
21	Talakadi Anjana	Total – 09 Herbal - 03 Mineral - 06	Haratala, Manashila, Sphatika, Shankha, Gandhaka, Saindhava lavana *Each 11.11%	66.67%
22	Tamradi Anjana 2	Total – 03 Herbal - 02 Mineral - 01	Tamra (33.33%)	33.33%

Table 2: Anjana yoga with herbomineral ingredients without specific disease indication

SI No:	Name of Yoga	No: of Ingredients	Rasa Dravya with proportion	Indications
1	Nayanaamrutham 1	Total - 15 Herbal - 08 Mineral - 07	Souveeranjana, Tuttha, Shankha Rasanjana, Varatika, Saindhava lavana, Samudraphena *Each 6.67% *Total 46.67%	All kind of eye disease
2	Garudanjanam 2	Total - 27 Herbal - 12 Mineral - 15	Saindhava lavana, Tuttha, Loha, Sphatika, Shankha, Varatika, Rasanjana, Manashila, Parada, Samudraphena, Souveeranjana, Kapala, Tamra, Tankana, Naga *3.70% each *Total 55.56%	Good vision – Garuda Drishti
3	Tamradi Anjanam 1	Total - 06 Herbal - 0 Mineral - 06	Tuttha (21.35%), Gandhaka (15.63%), Manashila (0.52%), Tamra, Abhraka, Kharpara (20.83% each) *Total 100%	Sarvanetra rujapaham
4	Saindhavadi anjanam	Total - 06 Herbal - 02 Mineral - 04	Saindhava lavana, Rasasindhura, Naga, Rasanjana *Each 16.67% *Total 66.67%	Sarvanetra gatamaya
5	Tarakadya Vatika	Total - 10 Herbal - 02 Mineral - 08	Rajata, Tamra, Kamsya, Tuttha, Shankha, Rasanjana, Kharpara, Rasasindhura, *Each 10% *Total 80%	Samastham netrajamayam

6	Girikarnikadi Anjana	Total - 07 Herbal - 06 Mineral - 01	Shankha (14.28%) *Total 14.28%	Netra rogas
7	Shiladi Anjanam	Total - 05 Herbal - 04 Mineral - 01	Manashila (20%) *Total 20%	Divya nakshatra darshanam
8	Mahanarikela Anjanam	Total - 14 Herbal - 10 Mineral - 04	Tuttha, Gairika, Saindhava lavana, Rasanjana Each 1.09% *Total 4.35%	96 netra rogas

Table 3: Anjana yoga with Herbal ingredients

SI No	Name of Yoga	Ingredients	Bhavana Dravya
1	Rasanjanadi Anjanam 1	Pippali, Ativisha	Goomutra
2	Marichanjanana	Maricha, Amalaki, Karanjabeeja	Bhringaraja swarasa
3	Darvadyadi Anjana	Daruharidra Rasakriya	-
4	Kumarika (Chandraprabha)varti	Tilapushpa, Maricha, Jatipushpa, Pippali	-
5	Dhatryanjanana	Triphala	Jala

Table 4: Anjana yoga with mineral components

SI No	Name of Yoga	Rasa Dravya
1	Tamradi Anjanam 1	Tamra, Abhraka, Kharpara, Manashila, Tuttha, Gandhaka *Total 100%
2	Gajakesara Vati	Manashila (25%), Naga (25%), Tuttha (50%) *Total 100%

Table 5: Individual Rasa Dravya as an ingredient in Anjana Yoga:

Mineral Drugs (Frequency)	Lowest %	Formulation	Highest %	Formulation
Tuttha(12)	1.09%	Mahanarikelanjanam	50%	Gajakesara Vati
Saindhava Lavana (13)	1.15%	Narikelanjanana	25%	Rasanjanadyanjanam 2
Tamra (7)	4.23%	Trikatukadyanjanam	33.33%	Tamradyanjanam 2
Loha	5%	Rasakriya 1	25%	Rasanjanadyanjanam 2
Rasasindhura/ Parada (5)	5%	Rasakriya 1	16.67%	Saindhavadyanjanam
Hingula (3)	1.25%	Rasanjanadyanjanam 2	6.66%	Anjana Varti
Manashila (9)	0.52%	Tamradyanjanam 1	38.71%	Shankhadi Vati
Haratala (3)	5%	Chandrakanjanana	11.11%	Talakadyanjanam
Naga (6)	5%	Rasakriya 1	25%	Rasanjanadyanjanam 2
Shankha (10)	3.23%	Shankhadi Vati	51.61%	Shankhadi Vati
Rasanjana (11)	1.25%	Rasanjanadyanjanam 2	16.67%	Saindhavadyanjanam
Souveeranjanana	5%	Rasakriya 1	12.5%	Netranjanam
Sphatika (8)	1.25%	Rasanjanadyanjanam 2	14.28%	Nayanamrutha 2
Samudraphena(7)	1.25%	Rasanjanadyanjanam 2	7.69%	Godanthadyanjanam
KukkutandaTwak	3.70%	Garudanjanam 2	14.28%	Chandraprabhanjanam
Gairika (5)	1.09%	Mahanarikelanjanam	5%	Rasakriya 1
Kharpara (3)	10%	Tarakadya Vatika	28.57%	Tilapushpanjanana
Gandhaka (2)	3.33%	Anjana Varti	15.63%	Tamradi Anjanam 1

DISCUSSION

Basavarajeeyam is a clinically oriented Ayurvedic text that emphasizes simple, practical, and disease-specific formulations, making it highly relevant for therapeutic use¹. It is organized into 24 *prakaraṇas*, each addressing the etiology, pathology, and treatment of individual diseases, with the final chapter dedicated exclusively to *rasa dravyas*. This structured approach highlights its strong therapeutic relevance and applicability in clinical practice.

It is observed that 31 anjana yogas out of 36 were composed of either single or multiple mineral ingredients. This emphasises on potency and targeted action, particularly through topical application. These yogas are designed not only for curative purposes in conditions like Abhishyanda and Timira but also for maintaining ocular health, focussing both on therapeutic and preventive aspects of Ayurveda. The selection of ingredients with Chakshushya, Lekhana, and Kapha-shamana properties further highlights a clear understanding of disease pathology and site-specific drug action, making these formulations relevant for both classical practice and future research exploration. Among 31 formulations *Tuttha* was seen as an ingredient in 12 anjana yogas. Owing to its Chakshushya, Lekhana, and Kandu–Krimi–Vishahara properties^{6,8} is repeatedly indicated for ocular diseases, particularly in conditions associated with itching, infection, and Kapha predominance. Kharpara⁶ and Gandhaka⁷ appear less frequently (3 and 2 times, respectively), yet both possess Netra roga hara properties.

Other *Rasa dravyas* fall within this range and also have classical evidence supporting their ocular-specific therapeutic actions. Abhraka used in netra durbalatha⁷ reflects its use in degenerative and weakness-related ocular conditions. Sphatika is Netraroga prashamani, lekhami, Snigdha, Rudhirasravarodhini⁸ demonstrates multi-

dimensional action including hemostatic and scraping properties. Gairika is Lochanayor hitham⁹ which further emphasizes its ocular benefits.

Among metal compounds, Naga, is chakshushya, Lekhanam is used in netra roga, madhumeha, upadrasvas^{7,9} indicates its dual systemic and ocular benefits along with scraping action. Tamra is Lekhana⁹, Sheethalam¹⁰, Netryam param lekhanam¹¹ shows its *oculo*-specific activity in expelling Pitta and Kapha from the eyes and possesses *Ropana* (wound-healing) properties.¹² Copper has a potent biocidal property and also helps in synthesis and stabilization of proteins along with angiogenesis; thus, may help in wound healing¹³. The Lauha Bhasma is Chakshushyam⁶, Veerye sheetham Lekhanam cha Atinetryam⁹ believed to improve blood quality and circulation, thereby augmenting ocular nourishment¹⁴.

Among Anjana, Souveeranjana is Netraamayaharam param, Vrana shodhaka ropaka⁹ demonstrates both disease alleviation and wound healing properties. Pushpanjana is Abhishyanda prashamanam param daha vinashanam⁹, Sarvakshi roganuth¹⁵ highlights its superiority in inflammatory and burning eye conditions. *Rasanjana*, a semisolid end product of heating homogenized milk-based decoction of *Berberis aristata*, is highly beneficial drug in ocular diseases. (*netrayoh paramam hitam*)¹⁶. According to Ayurveda Prakasha, Goat milk is used in preparation of Rasanjana¹⁷.

Shankha is indicated in netra roga (netra pushpa)⁷. The Anjana made out of this removes netra pushpa(ropana action) indicates corneal healing and regenerative potential. Pravala mentioned for netra daha and kandu⁷, Drushtiroga nishoodhanam⁹ reflects its application in burning sensation and visual disturbances. Varatika said as Netrya, Nayanathangaharini⁸ supports its direct ocular strengthening action. Samudraphena is Shishiram, Lekhanam, Chakshushyo

Khaphanashana⁸ indicates cooling along with Kaphahara and scraping action. Godanti and Kukkutanda twak bhasma is Sheetha⁸ which further strengthens the cooling base of these formulations.

Arsenic derivatives demonstrate potent Lekhana and Kapha-hara actions. Harathala is indicated in Drishti mandhya⁷(visual dullness). Manashila is mentioned as Kaphaghna, lekhana^{6,15} which emphasizes its Kapha-alleviating and scraping properties. Somala, indicated in Pakshma and netra vana, netra daha⁷ highlights its external therapeutic potency in eyelid disorders, ulcers, and burning sensation. Bahya prayogena Kshara karmakara param⁸.

Purified mercury helps in improving eye health¹⁸. Purified lead is described to have a specific therapeutic role in Prameha (diabetes)¹⁹, suggesting a potential benefit in modulating the pathophysiology of diabetic retinopathy. Hingula is Netra rogahara¹⁵, Lochanamayahara⁸ which indicates its action in ocular pathologies. Rasasindhoora's anti-inflammatory and anti-bacterial studies further supports its therapeutic potency in inflammatory and infective ocular conditions. Tankana is said to be Vividha vana nashana, Kapha visleshano⁸ demonstrates wound-healing and Kapha-separating action. Saindhava lavana (Lunati iti lavanam); that which has chedana ppty. Its Chakshushya, Avidahi- (unlike regular salts) property²⁰ reflects its unique non-irritant nature and specific suitability in ocular therapy.

These formulations act through multiple therapeutic pathways to manage a broad spectrum of ocular disorders, including antioxidant protection, anti-inflammatory effects, antimicrobial activity, and promotion of tissue nourishment and regeneration.

CONCLUSION

Ayurvedic scholars have emphasized the importance of the eyes, stating “Sarvendriyanam nayanam pradhanam”, highlighting their supremacy among all sense organs. Ayurvedic classics describe several Kriyakalpas for the management of netra rogas, among which Anjana holds a significant therapeutic role. Its mode of application ensures direct drug delivery to ocular tissues, prolongs contact time, and enhances therapeutic efficacy, thereby establishing Anjana as a valuable intervention in the management of Netra rogas.

The exploration of Anjana yoga in *Basavarajeeyam* highlights their significant therapeutic and preventive relevance in the management of ocular disorders. This study identified 36 Anjana yogas, mostly herbo-mineral, used for conditions like Abhishyanda and Timira. Overall, Anjana emerges as a practical and effective topical approach with both preventive and therapeutic value in eye care, warranting further validation and standardization for clinical use.

REFERENCES

1. Badami CS, Hussain G. Wound healing applications as per Basavarajeeyam. *World J Pharm Med Res.* 2022;8(7):91–96.
2. Sharma AR. *Sushruta Samhita of Maharshi Sushrut: Sutrasthana.* Varanasi: Chaukhambha Surbharati Prakashan; 2010. Verse 46/31
3. Vagbhata. *Ashtanga Hridaya* (English translation by K.R. Srikantha Murthy). Varanasi: Chaukhambha Krishnadas Academy; Reprint 2014. Sutrasthana, Dinacharya Adhyaya.
4. Kadibagil V, Sharma G. Critical review on nano-ophthalmology of collyriums used in Ayurveda. *Int J Biol Pharm Allied Sci.*

- 2021;10(4):1332–1345. Access link (DOI): <https://doi.org/10.31032/IJBPAS/2021/10.4.5451>
5. Krishnamurthy MS, translator. *Basavarajeeyam* (English translation). Varanasi: Chaukhambha Orientalia; 2019. Netra Roga Chikitsa Adhyaya.
 6. Tripathi I. Rasendrasarasangraha (Savimarśa ‘Rasavidyotini’ Hindi commentary). 2nd ed. Varanasi: Chaukhambha Orientalia; 1998. Pratham Adhyaya; p. 51 - 70.
 7. Rasa Tantra Sarah Evam Siddha Prayoga Sangraha- Part I, 8th Edn. Ajmer, India: Krishan Gopal Ayurveda Bhawan; 1990. 60 - 110p.
 8. Shastri K, translator. *Rasa Tarangini* (English translation). Varanasi: Motilal Banarsidass; 2012. Chapter 11 - 16.
 9. Shastri K, translator. *Rasa Tarangini* (English translation). Varanasi: Motilal Banarsidass; 2012. Chapter 17 - 22.
 10. Acharya YT. *Rasāmṛtam* (English translation by Joshi D). 1st ed. Varanasi: Chaukhambha Sanskrit Bhawan; 1998. Chapter 3.
 11. Somadeva. *Rasendra Chudamani* (Hindi commentary by Mishra SN). Reprint ed. Varanasi: Chaukhambha Orientalia; 2014. Chapter 14.
 12. National Institute of Indian Medical Heritage. *Susruta Samhita*, Sutrasthana, Ch. 46, Verses 327–328. E-Book. Central Council for Research in Ayurvedic Sciences (CCRAS); 2010. Available from: <http://niimh.nic.in/ebooks/esushruta/>
 13. Borkow G. Using copper to improve the well-being of the skin. *Current Chemical Biology*. 2014;8(2):89–102. doi:10.2174/2212796809666150227223857. Available from: <https://doi.org/10.2174/2212796809666150227223857>
 14. Patel MK, Patel H. Exploring Ayurvedic formulations for ocular health: a review of traditional knowledge and contemporary research. *World J Pharm Pharm Sci*. 2025;14(8):183–194. doi:10.20959/wjpps20258-30393. Available from: <https://doi.org/10.20959/wjpps20258-30393>
 15. Mishra SN. *Rasaratna Samucchaya*. In: Vagbhat AS, editor. 3rd chapter, verse 145. Varanasi: Chaukhambha Orientaliya; 2011. p. 145–146.
 16. National Institute of Indian Medical Heritage. *Bhavaprakasha Nighantu* E-Book. Central Council for Research in Ayurvedic Sciences (CCRAS); 2012. Poorva Khandam, Mishra Prakarana, Ch. 02, Verse 179. Available from: <http://niimh.nic.in/ebooks/e-Nighantu/bhavaprakashanighantu/>
 17. Asore G, Sheth SS, Suthar KB. Pharmaceutical and analytical study of Rasanjan w.s.r. Ayurved Prakash Samhita. *International Ayurvedic Medical Journal*. 2020 Dec [cited 2026 Feb 9];8(??):5282-5286. doi:10.46607/IAMJ1208122020. Available from: https://www.iamj.in/posts/2020/images/upload/5282_5286_1.pdf
 18. National Institute of Indian Medical Heritage. *Bhavaprakasha Nighantu* E-Book. Central Council for Research in Ayurvedic Sciences (CCRAS); 2012. Poorva Khandam, Mishra Prakaranam, Ch. 08, Verse 80. Available from: <http://niimh.nic.in/ebooks/e-Nighantu/bhavaprakashanighantu/>
 19. National Institute of Indian Medical Heritage. *Bhavaprakasha Nighantu* E-Book. Central Council for Research in Ayurvedic Sciences (CCRAS); 2012. Poorva Khandam, Mishra Prakarana, Ch. 08, Verse 33. Available from: <http://niimh.nic.in/ebooks/e-Nighantu/bhavaprakashanighantu/>

20. Kalyanshetty PG, Jadhav V, Naganur V. Critical analysis of Anjana in systemic diseases. *J Ayurveda Integr Med Sci.* 2021;6(3):121–125.
doi:10.21760/jaims.v6i3.1314. Available from: <https://jaims.in/jaims/article/view/1314>

HOW TO CITE: Arya J. P., Govinda Sharma K., Prajwal Sanakyanavar, Suchindra R., Surabhi Gopal, Gayathri Sajeev, Review Of Anjana Formulations in Basavarajeeyam and Their Clinical Significance, *Int. J. of Pharm. Sci.*, 2026, Vol 4, Issue 5, 2752-2760, <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.20133225>

